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THE DILEMMA OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article explains the current state of the English language in educational discourse. Historical facts and Ages of the English language explain the diversity of English. It shows interweaving and interaction of the Internet and the English language. The author puts forward the idea of witnessing the emergence of a new type of the Global English language, as the spread of varieties of the English language (dialects, variants) will lead to a division into incomprehensible new languages, and in this case, the fate of the Latin language awaits the English language. Linguistic and extra linguistic transformations of the English language as global ones, has changed the bases of how it is taught and learnt. The shift of the conversational language to its written realization through social nets and messengers must be taken into consideration while teaching. The qualitative research methodology: observation and description analysis are mainly used. The author concludes that the importance and coverage of the English language traces to its historical roots, GlobalEnglish-approach to language teaching helps to save its international status, the WWW changes the language on different levels: lexical; morphological; syntactical; phonetic etc. Besides the linguistic dilemma teacher must meet psychological challenges in language skills development.

Introduction. With increasing global demand for English proficiency, English has become a global industry. English proficiency in education, science, technology, engineering etc. as a part of the modernization agenda is a major part of authorities initiatives. English is a prestige

language in many contexts. Its spread as a global language has resulted in the emergence of a number of related fields of research within applied linguistics and language teaching, including English as an International Language, English as a

Foreign Language, English as a Lingua Franca, World Englishes, ESP etc.

We follow the idea of researchers who “groups these fields under the one umbrella term of Global Englishes in its exploration of the impact of the global spread of English on English users and learners. Our use of the term Global Englishes is not a rebranding exercise, but, rather, a consolidation one. As independent research fields have been exploring the diverse use of English associated with its global spread, as well as its implications, a term is needed to unite the shared agendas, ideologies and calls for change to pedagogy” [11] If we ask about the purposes of teaching English, the majority of teachers will identify communication as the primary one.

The similar question about the purpose of learning English for students is also communication. Both teachers and students acknowledge the importance of English on a global level. Other reasons for teaching and learning English included developing literacy skills, and the usefulness of English for future survival and employment.[9, c.5] The English language is an especially important one not only for a society that is multilingual and where students speak a colloquial variety of English outside the classroom, but it is especially important in education in which English is the medium of teaching and learning for most subjects in mainstream education.

In many countries, in Russia particularly, students do not speak English as their predominant language and even as a second one thus it also lengthen the journey towards academic English that opens doors in the academic world.

International research [6; 7] suggests that it takes a minimum of 5 years for learners for whom English is a nondominant language to develop competence in academic English.

The dilemma noted by teachers is:

- what type/variant/dialect/ of English should be chosen for mastering to achieve learners’ personal educational goals;
- how to provide learners with exposure to plenty of English vocabulary;
- how to ensure that learners notice the differences between scientific-specific language and everyday varieties of language;
- should we consider Global Englishes for Language Teaching as a ground-breaking attempt to unite discussions on the pedagogical implications of the global spread of English into a single text for researchers and practicing teachers.

Methodology

The qualitative research methodology is mainly used for the research. The subject of the research is natural and not predefined. It is viewed in the context of collective experience. The research focuses more on suggesting causes, effects, possible relationships etc. Observation and description are used to evaluate knowledge, case study, action research, disclosure analysis and are based on the quality of the phenomenon.

What is the English Language?

The English language is in transition, it is taking new forms. It has changed substantially for its Seven Ages (I.- Pre-English period – c.AD 450; II.- Early Old English – c.450- c.850; III. Later Old English (c.850-1100); IV. Middle English (c.1100-1450); V. Early Modern English (c.1450-1750); VI. Modern English (c.1750-1950); VII. Late Modern English (c.1950-),

reflecting patterns of contact with other languages and events. It is remarkable for its diversity, its propensity to change and be changed. English is no longer spoken only by its native speakers and by those who learn English in order to communicate with native speakers. The question is “Who are native speakers?” the British, the Americans, the Indian, the Canadian, the Australian.

While interacting with the local dialects and dialects spoken by the inhabitants of the new British colonies, such variants of the modern English language such as American, Indian, Australian, Irish, Canadian, African, New Zealand appeared from British English.

Moreover, within the British Isles there is no homogeneity of the language: dialects and variants in pronunciation (BBC English, Royal English, Advanced English) The main differences are in phonetics, in intonation, articulation and pronunciation. Phonetics is under the influence of varieties of English that has caused a number of linguists to question the use of Received Pronunciation pronunciation models in the teaching of English [8].

In recent years native speakers have become minority stakeholders of English. The use of the English language as a global lingua franca requires intelligibility and setting and maintenance of standards.

The Internet is the electronic “flagship” of Global English And this is logical, both as a consequence of the status of the English language as the language of international communication, and as a consequence of the fact that the Internet was created in an English-speaking country. Thus, at the stage of its origin and development, the Internet «lived» exclusively in the English-speaking space, and, consequently, the

English language forces users to reckon with it.

According to statistics, 75 % of the world's mail is written in English, about 80% of the information stored on electronic media is written in English. And although more than a thousand languages are currently used on the network, it is likely that the influence of English will increase, since it plays an important role in software. As D. Crystal ironically noted, a significant obstacle to the global spread of the English language could have arisen in the previous generation if Chinese had been the native language of Bill Gates [5].

Perhaps we are currently witnessing the emergence of a new type of global English – the English language of the virtual space. Although the English language itself has changed over many centuries and under the influence of many factors (political, economic, social, cultural, etc.), but none of the factors can compete with digital technologies either in terms of speed or scale of making changes.

Nowadays many scientists and native speakers express fears that the English language will be transformed beyond recognition thanks to the Internet, and globalization will significantly accelerate this pace. Linguists find a number of differences between the English language of native English speakers, and the English language as a means of international communication – GlobalLanguage, which is massively studied, mainly using the same authentic textbooks in all parts of the world.

But Global English is a phenomenon that is not perceived unambiguously from the position of «language and culture are two sides of the same coin». Whose culture does Global English verbalize? The positive

aspect of this process is that the universal command of the English language provides a natural desire of a person for mutual understanding on a “global scale”.

Occupation of the “virtual space” by the English language once again proves its claims to play the role of lingua franca, the language of international communication, which is used in almost each sphere of human life and society. The current situation with English is unique in its own way.

Never before any of the languages has received such wide distribution and coverage in such a short time. T. MacArthur expresses his opinion that the spread of varieties of the English language (dialects, variants) will lead to a division into incomprehensible new languages, and in this case, the fate of the Latin language awaits the English language [10].

English is adapting to the technical capabilities of the virtual space and it is the main means of creating a new communicative environment, which reflects all the specifics of its use.

Conclusion

The importance and coverage of the English language traces to its historical roots and nowadays undergo some transformation in form and content. Global-English-approach to language teaching helps to save international status of the English language and fulfill restrictive function nevertheless it deprives the language from native British speakers. The Internet and computer-mediated communication contribute to not only the ways of teaching the language but also to the language itself. As like any other phenomenon that is borrowed by the virtual space from the real one, English acquires additional characteristics and features. For example, unlike the real space, the speech of the virtual space has only a written implementation, which means that it excludes additional connotative shades that can be expressed by facial expressions, emotions, the speaker's behavior, etc., but it has compensatory capabilities in the form of emoticons and pictograms. The WWW changes morphology, syntactic and semantics of the English language.

References:

1. Zerkina N. N. Lingvisticheskie i eticheskie transformatsii kommunikatsii v internet prostranstve : monografiya [Elektronnyi resurs], Polidiskursivnoe prostranstvo: slovo, tekst, kommunikatsiya, Magnitogorsk, MGTU im. G.I. Nosova, 2017.
2. Zerkina N. N., Degtyareva K. S., Smirnova A. V. Organizatsiya i samoorganizatsiya obucheniya angliiskomu yazyku s ispol'zovaniem sovremennykh IT tekhnologii, Fenomen cheloveka, 2015, pp. 53–156.
3. Kristal D. Angliiskii yazyk kak global'nyi, Moscow, Ves' Mir, 2001, 238 p.
4. Crystal, David. Language and the Internet Second Edition, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2006.
5. Crystal David. Internet Linguistics: A Student Guide. Routledge. Taylor & Francis Group, London and New York, 2011, p. 1–2.
6. Cummins, J., & Man, E. Y.-F. Academic language: What is it and how do we acquire it? In J. Cummins & C. Davison (Eds.), International handbook of English language teaching, part two, New York, Springer, 2007, pp. 797- 810.

7. Demie F. English as an additional language pupils: How long does it take to acquire English fluency? [Elektronnyi resurs] *Language and Education*, no. 27(1), pp. 59-69. 2013. URL:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2012.682580> (accessed 20 September 2021).
8. Global English and the teaching of pronunciation [Elektronnyi resurs] URL: <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/global-english-teaching-pronunciation>
9. Jones, S. A., Yeo, L. R-C., Yeo, K. K. J., Seilhamer, M. F., Loh, M. Y., & Ho, H. L. Dilemmas in English teaching and learning: Singaporean primary classrooms booklet 2 [PDF file] [Elektronnyi resurs], Singapore, National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, 2019, URL: <https://www.researchgate.net/scientific-contributions/Jones-S-A-Yeo-K-K-J-Seilhamer-M-F-Loh-M-Y-Ho-H-L-Yeo-L-R-C-2158377545>
10. McArthur T. *The English language*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1998, 247p.
11. Rose H., & Galloway, N. Copyright page. In *Global Englishes for Language Teaching* [Elektronnyi resurs], Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2019, URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316678343>